

**FORMULATION, DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF
MUCOADHESIVE BUCCAL TABLET CONTAINING LASMIDITAN****Kanchan B. Tarle*¹, Prof. Mitesh P. Sonawane²**Department of pharmaceuticals, Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy, Manur
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Article Received on 04 June 2026,

Article Revised on 25 June 2026,

Article Published on 01 July 2026,

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India.**How to cite this Article:** Kanchan B. Tarle*¹,
Prof. Mitesh P. Sonawane². (2026). Formulation,
Development And Evaluation of Mucoadhesive
Buccal Tablet Containing Lasmiditan. World
Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(13),
162-178.This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.**ABSTRACT**

The present study aimed to develop and evaluate mucoadhesive buccal tablets of Lasmiditan using Carbopol 934P as a mucoadhesive polymer and different concentrations of superdisintegrants such as Sodium Starch Glycolate, Croscarmellose Sodium, and Crospovidone. The tablets were prepared by direct compression and evaluated for pre-compression and post-compression parameters, drug content, swelling index, and in vitro drug release. FTIR and DSC studies confirmed the compatibility of Lasmiditan with the selected excipients. All formulations showed acceptable flow properties, hardness, friability, and drug content. Among the formulations, TF6 exhibited the best performance with 98.75% drug content, 0.36% friability, and 94.19% drug release within 30 minutes. The results indicated that increasing the concentration of superdisintegrants improved drug release and

tablet performance. Therefore, TF6 was identified as the optimized formulation for buccal delivery of Lasmiditan, offering rapid drug release and good pharmaceutical characteristics.

KEYWORDS: Mucoadhesive, Buccal, Lasmiditan, Direct Compression.**INTRODUCTION**

Bioadhesion is the state of interfacial molecular attractive forces between the surfaces of biological substrates and natural or synthetic polymers that allow the polymer to adhere to biological surfaces for a long period. Among the several drug delivery modalities, the oral

route is probably the most preferred by both patients and medical experts. However, there are disadvantages to oral drug delivery, such as gastrointestinal (GI) tract enzymatic degradation and hepatic first-pass metabolism, which prevent oral administration of various pharmaceutical types, including peptides and proteins. Consequently, additional absorptive mucosals are considered as potential sites for medication delivery. The mucosal linings of the nasal, rectal, vaginal, ocular, and oral canals have distinct benefits over peroral administration drug delivery routes for systemic activity.^[1] Avoiding first-pass effects and presystemic elimination in the GI tract are two of these advantages. The buccal region of the oral cavity is a preferred site for drug delivery because of its simple mode of administration. Buccal drug delivery is the method of delivering a desired medication through the oral cavity's buccal mucosal membrane. Both trans-mucosal (systemic effect) and mucosal (local effect) drug delivery are effectively accomplished with this technique. The first scenario seeks to achieve a site-specific release of the drug on the mucosa, whereas the second scenario involves drug absorption past the mucosal barrier to reach the systemic circulation.^[2,3]

Mucoadhesive Buccal Drug Delivery System

Mucoadhesive drug delivery techniques make use of the bioadhesion of certain polymers, which become sticky when hydrated and enable the long-term targeting of a medicine to a particular part of the body. The ability to maintain a delivery system in one location for an extended period of time is especially appealing for both local and systemic medication bioavailability. Since mucoadhesion has the ability to prevent either hepatic first-pass drug activation or degradation by gastrointestinal contents, there has been a lot of interest in its pharmacological implications in recent years.^[4]

MATERIAL

Lasmiditan was provided from Ichem Laboratories, Surat. Carbopol 934P, Lactose, Mannitol & Micro Crystalline Cellulose obtained from Balaji drugs or Sodium Starch Glycolate, Crosscarmellose Sodium, Crosspovidone & Mg. Stearate obtained from Research Lab Fine Chemical Industries, Mumbai.

METHOD

Spectrometric Analysis

- In a 100 ml volumetric flask, 10 mg of precisely weighed Lasmiditan was dissolved in 70 ml of methanol to determine the analytical wavelength (λ_{max}) of Lasmiditan. A stock

solution containing 100 µg/ml was made by adding methanol once the volume reached 100 ml. To obtain a 10 µg/ml solution, they diluted 2.5 ml of this stock with 10 ml of methanol. The absorbance at 215 nm was the highest when this solution was scanned with a UV-visible spectrophotometer between 200 and 400 nm. The stock for the calibration curve was used to make solutions at different concentrations (5–25 µg/ml), and the absorbance of the solutions at 215 nm was measured using methanol as the solvent.^[5]

- Lasmiditan's maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was measured by precisely weighing 10 mg of the medication and dissolving it in 20 ml of methanol in a 100 ml volumetric flask. The volume was then increased to 100 milliliters by making the standard solution with phosphate buffer. One milliliter was further diluted with the same buffer to generate ten milliliters, yielding a 10 µg/ml solution. Using a UV-visible spectrophotometer to scan the solution between 200 and 400 nm, the λ_{max} was found to be 215 nm. For the calibration curve, a range of concentrations from 5 to 25 µg/ml were created, and their absorbance was measured using UV spectroscopy with phosphate buffer as the solvent at 215 nm.^[5]

Determination of Preformulation Parameters

It's crucial to take into account variables like tapped density, bulk density, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index, and angle of repose when researching the flow and packing characteristics of powders and granules. Both before and after tapping, bulk and tapped densities quantify the amount of mass contained in a specific volume. The angle of repose provides insight into how the friction between the particles influences their accumulation. Carr's index indicates how compressible the particles are, whereas Hausner's ratio helps us understand how easily the powder flows. These characteristics are crucial for efficient powder handling in industries like materials research, food, and medicines.^[6]

FTIR

An effective method for examining how medications interact with polymers and other excipients during storage is infrared spectroscopy. In this instance, it was employed to investigate the interactions between excipients and Lasmiditan. The IR spectra of the drug alone and a physical combination of the drug plus excipients were examined to search for any chemical alterations. If the spectra are different, there is an interaction between the chemicals. Samples stored in a stability chamber were assessed using an FTIR spectrophotometer

operating in the 4000-400 cm^{-1} wavelength range. The same method was used to assess various drug-loaded powders after lasmiditan and excipients were mixed in a 1:1 ratio.^[7]

Differential Scanning Colorimetry (DSC)

A Shimadzu DSC-60 plus was used to perform differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) on Lasmiditan and its excipients in order to examine their thermal characteristics. To observe their thermal behavior, samples of Lasmiditan and the excipients, combined in a 1:1 ratio, were heated in aluminum pans from 25°C to 300°C at a rate of 10°C per minute.^[8]

Solubility of API

Lasmiditan solubility tests can determine how much of the medication dissolves in various solvents. Excess Lasmiditan is added to the solvent at a particular temperature and stirred until it dissolves entirely. Once the remaining undissolved drug has been separated, the amount of dissolved Lasmiditan is measured using methods such as UV spectroscopy. This research advances our knowledge of the drug's solubility, which is essential to both its effectiveness and the body's capacity to absorb it.

Tablet Preparation

Carbopol 934P, a mucoadhesive polymer, was used in the direct compression process to create Lasmiditan buccal tablets. Every single component, including excipients and tablet polymer, was carefully weighed in accordance with the batch formula in order to obtain a uniform particle size before being passed through sieve number 40. The drug and all other materials except lubricants were put on butter paper using a stainless steel spatula. After that, the materials were mixed for ten minutes in an inflated polyethylene pouch in ascending weight order. Once the ingredients were evenly mixed, lubricant was added and swirled again for two minutes. An 8 mm punch on a rotating tablet punching machine was used to compress the resulting mix for each formulation.^[9,10]

Composition of Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablet

Table 1: Composition of Lasmiditan Tablet.

Sr. No	Ingredients	TF1	TF2	TF3	TF4	TF5	TF6	TF7	TF8
1	Lasmiditan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
2	Carbopol 934P	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
3	Sodium Starch Glycolate	5	20	5	5	20	20	5	20
4	Crosscarmellose Sodium	5	20	20	20	5	20	5	5
5	Crospovidone	5	5	5	20	20	20	20	5
6	MCC	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

7	Mg. Stearate	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
8	Lactose	67.5	37.5	52.5	37.5	37.5	22.5	52.5	52.5
9	Mannitol	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Tablet weight		250							

Note: The above ingredients are all in mg.

Determination of Post- Formulation Parameters

A Vernier Caliper is used to measure thickness in millimeters; a hardness tester is used to measure hardness by gradually applying force until the tablet breaks; the results are expressed in kilograms per centimeter; weight variation is checked by weighing twenty randomly chosen tablets; and a friabilator is used to measure friability, which is the percentage of tablet weight lost after the tablets are rotated. These tests make sure the tablets fulfill the necessary requirements for durability and uniformity.^[11]

Drug Content

Twenty tablets were broken into powder, and 100 mg of the powder was combined with 100 ml of a phosphate buffer solution with a pH of 6.8 to determine the drug concentration. After 30 minutes of stirring, the mixture was filtered. A UV-visible spectrophotometer was used to test the filtered solution's absorbance at 215 nm after it had been diluted with the same 6.8 pH phosphate buffer.^[12]

Swelling Index

The swelling index of the buccal tablets was determined by measuring the percentage weight gain of the tablet. One tablet from each formulation was placed in a Petri dish containing 20 mL phosphate buffer pH 6.8 maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. At predetermined intervals (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 min), the tablet was removed, blotted carefully with tissue paper to remove excess surface water and weighed. The swelling index was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Swelling index} = \left\{ \frac{(M_t - M_o)}{M_o} \right\} \times 100$$

Were,

S.I. = Swelling index

M_t = weight of tablet at the time (t)

M_o = weight of tablet at time 0.

In-vitro drug release studies

The release rate of Lasmiditan from Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablet (equivalent to 10 mg of Lasmiditan) can be measured using the USP-II tablet dissolving testing device at a rotation speed of 50 rpm. The dissolving test was conducted using 900 milliliters of 6.8 Phosphate Buffer solutions at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Every two minutes, a 5 ml aliquot sample was taken out and replaced with fresh medium. The amount of Lasmiditan in each medicinal solution was measured using a spectrophotometer calibrated to 215 nm.^[13]

Table 2: Dissolution Parameters.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Specifications
1	USP dissolution device	Type II [Paddle method]
2	Dissolution medium volume	900 ml
3	Rotation speed	50 rpm
4	Temperature	$37^\circ\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$
5	Medium of dissolution	Phosphate buffer pH 6.8
6	Sample withdraw at each time interval	5ml

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Spectrometric Analysis

- Lasmiditan's maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) was found to be 215 nm using UV spectroscopy, as Fig. 1 illustrates.

Fig. 1: Analytical wavelength (λ_{max}) of Lasmiditan.

The standard calibration curve for Lasmiditan shows an excellent linear connection between concentration and absorbance; its slope is $y = 0.0238x + 0.0134$, and its coefficient of regression value is $R^2 = 0.999$ (Fig. 2).

Table 3: Concentration and Absorbance value for Lasmiditan in methanol.

Sr. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 215 nm
1.	5	0.125
2.	10	0.260
3.	15	0.371
4.	20	0.488
5.	25	0.605

Fig. 2: Calibration curve of Lasmiditan in Methanol.

- Lasmiditan (10 mg/ml) had its UV spectra examined between 200 and 400 nm. 6.8 phosphate buffer. At 215 nm, Lasmiditan displayed its maximum absorption wavelength. (Fig.3).

Fig.3: UV Spectrum of Lasmiditan in 6.8 Phosphate Buffer.

A 6.8 pH phosphate buffer was used to produce a Lasmiditan calibration curve. With a high regression value of $R^2 = 0.9988$ and the equation $y = 0.0206x + 0.0682$, the curve displayed a straight-line connection within the concentration range of 5–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The Lasmiditan calibration curve in this buffer is displayed in Figure 4.

Table 4: Concentration and Absorbance value for Lasmiditan in 6.8 Phosphate Buffer.

Sr. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 215 nm
1.	5	0.172
2.	10	0.268
3.	15	0.386
4.	20	0.478
5.	25	0.582

Fig.4: Lasmiditan calibration curve in 6.8 Phosphate Buffer.**Pre-compression evaluation of Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablet****Table 5: Precompression evaluation of Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablet.**

Formulation	Bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density(g/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose (θ)
TF1	0.50 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.04	12.28 ± 0.06	1.14 ± 0.42	$28.2^\circ \pm 0.04$
TF2	0.48 ± 0.03	0.54 ± 0.02	11.11 ± 0.04	1.12 ± 0.36	$27.8^\circ \pm 0.02$
TF3	0.44 ± 0.06	0.52 ± 0.08	15.38 ± 0.08	1.18 ± 0.40	$29.6^\circ \pm 0.14$
TF4	0.47 ± 0.02	0.53 ± 0.04	11.32 ± 0.02	1.12 ± 0.32	$30.1^\circ \pm 0.08$
TF5	0.49 ± 0.05	0.56 ± 0.06	12.50 ± 0.05	1.14 ± 0.30	$27.4^\circ \pm 0.11$
TF6	0.52 ± 0.03	0.58 ± 0.11	10.34 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.34	$25.8^\circ \pm 0.08$
TF7	0.51 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.04	12.06 ± 0.06	1.13 ± 0.38	$28.6^\circ \pm 0.06$
TF8	0.45 ± 0.05	0.51 ± 0.04	11.76 ± 0.04	1.13 ± 0.40	$30.5^\circ \pm 0.03$

When pre-compression parameters were taken into account, the powder mixes of all eight formulations displayed bulk densities between 0.45 and 0.42 g/ml and tapped densities between 0.51 and 0.58 g/ml. The angle of repose ranged from 25.8° to 30.5° , the Hausner's

ratio from 1.11 to 1.18, and the Carr's index from 10.34% to 15.38%. These results highlight the blends' exceptional compressibility and flowability as well as their adherence to recognized pharmaceutical standards.

FTIR

Fig 5: Pure Drug Lasmiditan.

Fig 6: Pure Drug Lasmiditan.

After preparing a 1:1 mixture of lasmiditan and all excipients, these mixes were examined using an FTIR spectrophotometer, which recorded their infrared spectra between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} .

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Fig. 7: Pure drug Lasmiditan.

Fig. 8: Lasmiditan + Excipients.

DSC was used to examine the preparation's thermal behavior in order to ascertain its melting point, crystallinity, breakdown, and drug-excipient interaction. Lasmiditan's DSC shows that it is compatible with all excipients, with the latter exhibiting a discernible endothermic peak at 196°C at 11.99 minutes.

Saturation solubility studies for drug

Table 6: Lasmiditan pure drug in various solvents.

Solvent	Solubility
Ethanol	Slightly Soluble
Methanol	Freely Soluble
Water	Sparingly Soluble

Lasmiditan's solubility in several solvents was assessed using saturation solubility experiments. Lasmiditan is easily soluble in methanol, according to the findings.

Evaluation result of Tablet

Table 7: Evaluation result of Mucoadhesive Tablet.

Formulation	Weight variation (%)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)
TF1	248.4±1.54	3.40±0.05	2.80±0.10	0.45±0.08
TF2	252.2±1.20	3.26±0.10	2.90±0.18	0.43±0.04
TF3	248.8±1.58	3.22±0.07	2.73±0.25	0.44±0.06
TF4	247.10±1.66	3.30±0.18	2.71±0.05	0.42±0.06
TF5	255.2±1.18	3.45±0.10	3.10±0.10	0.41±0.10
TF6	250.6±1.63	3.20±0.15	2.60±0.15	0.36±0.02
TF7	246.15±1.53	3.25±0.14	2.76±0.08	0.44±0.15
TF8	253.56±1.80	3.15±0.20	2.50±0.20	0.40±0.02

Based on its balanced physical attributes and exceptional performance, F6 stands out as the optimized batch among the assessed tablet formulations. It maintains sufficient hardness (3.20 ± 0.15 kg/cm²) for mechanical strength without sacrificing disintegration and exhibits a weight fluctuation (250.6 ± 1.63 mg), showing good content homogeneity. Easy swallowing and packaging are guaranteed by its reasonable thickness (2.60 ± 0.15 mm). Among all batches, F6 exhibits the lowest friability ($0.36 \pm 0.02\%$), indicating outstanding resistance to chipping or abrasion during handling. According to these characteristics, F6 appears to have the best overall balance between manufacturability, mechanical integrity, and compressibility, making it the most appropriate optimized formulation for additional development.

Drug content

Table 8: Mucoadhesive Tablet Drug Content.

Formulation	Drug Content
TF1	94.36±0.12
TF2	95.28±0.08
TF3	94.55±0.40
TF4	96.80±0.33
TF5	95.29±0.45
TF6	98.75±0.20
TF7	96.26±0.16
TF8	95.72±0.24

Table 7 shows that the drug content varies between 94.36% and 98.75%. The results demonstrate that the techniques employed in this study to develop the Mucoadhesive buccal tablet were successful in producing a formulation with a constant dosage of medication.

Swelling Index

For Lasmiditan, the swelling index for all batches F1 – F8 was determined.

Table 9: Swelling Index for Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablet.

Time (Min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	15.20 ± 0.11	12.39 ± 0.24	18.78 ± 0.14	15.24 ± 0.20	11.45 ± 0.19	24.10 ± 0.15	20.22 ± 0.10	16.38 ± 0.12
10	26.45 ± 0.21	25.86 ± 0.18	24.13 ± 0.20	30.58 ± 0.30	26.92 ± 0.22	40.33 ± 0.25	32.60 ± 0.15	24.20 ± 0.16
15	34.20 ± 0.20	32.78 ± 0.19	30.87 ± 0.18	44.40 ± 0.25	38.88 ± 0.18	55.67 ± 0.20	45.05 ± 0.21	30.24 ± 0.14
20	38.55 ± 0.29	38.14 ± 0.32	40.97 ± 0.27	48.43 ± 0.25	44.89 ± 0.27	60.78 ± 0.25	50.65 ± 0.30	42.12 ± 0.15
25	42.32 ± 0.18	42.95 ± 0.22	48.12 ± 0.24	54.76 ± 0.21	50.21 ± 0.30	63.20 ± 0.33	54.26 ± 0.29	48.28 ± 0.22
30	46.80 ± 0.25	50.67 ± 0.24	55.42 ± 0.22	58.66 ± 0.38	56.32 ± 0.27	68.33 ± 0.28	58.98 ± 0.33	55.11 ± 0.16

*Indicates (N=3) ± SD

Among all batches, F6 exhibited the highest swelling index ($68.33 \pm 0.28\%$) at 30 Min, suggesting a superior water absorption capacity, likely due to an optimal concentration of polymers.

Mucoadhesive Strength

Table 10: Mucoadhesive Strength of F1-F8 Batch.

Formulation Code	Mucoadhesive Strength (gm)
F1	15.22 ± 0.24
F2	22.14 ± 0.11
F3	22.64 ± 0.18
F4	24.39 ± 0.30
F5	20.12 ± 0.22
F6	34.18 ± 0.08
F7	26.32 ± 0.26
F8	30.26 ± 0.12

The mucoadhesive strength data for the lasmiditan buccal tablet formulations F1 to F8 reveals significant variation among the batches. Formulation F8 exhibited the highest mucoadhesive strength (34.18 ± 0.12 g), indicating strong adhesion to the mucosal surface, which is crucial for prolonged retention and effective drug delivery.

In vitro Dissolution study

The IP Monograph of the Lasmiditan tablet was used to assess the rate of dissolution of both the pure drug Lasmiditan and the Mucoadhesive tablet. When a solvent was added, the mucoadhesive tablet typically dissolved much more quickly than the powdered medication, according to the results (Table: 8).

Table 11: Cumulative % Drug release of Mucoadhesive tablet.

% Drug Release (min)	0	5	10	15	20	25	30
TF1	0.00	22.16±0.02	30.66±0.08	42.13±0.04	58.67±0.02	68.10±0.12	80.42±0.04
TF2	0.00	26.42±0.04	36.92±0.06	52.57±0.02	67.35±0.04	78.37±0.06	86.45±0.08
TF3	0.00	28.68±0.02	38.95±0.04	56.19±0.02	70.88±0.06	80.10±0.08	88.92±0.02
TF4	0.00	31.15±0.04	44.23±0.04	58.57±0.02	72.18±0.08	82.14±0.06	90.06±0.04
TF5	0.00	30.07±0.08	46.38±0.06	58.39±0.04	76.12±0.04	80.64±0.02	89.44±0.04
TF6	0.00	34.28±0.02	48.41±0.06	60.16±0.08	78.33±0.04	86.45±0.06	94.19±0.02
TF7	0.00	25.14±0.08	33.54±0.08	46.45±0.04	56.55±0.06	68.37±0.02	82.16±0.04
TF8	0.00	26.12±0.08	44.20±0.04	56.80±0.02	68.57±0.06	80.01±0.02	92.82±0.02

Using a USP single station apparatus, all eight formulations (TF1 to TF8) underwent in vitro dissolving testing. Samples were taken every five minutes and measured at 215 nm. In comparison to TF6, formulations TF1, TF2, TF3, TF5, TF6, TF7, and TF8 showed reduced solubility and slower drug release (Table 8). As seen in Figs. 11 and 12, formulation F6 exhibited the most effective and reliable drug release within 30 minutes.

Fig. 9: % drug release of TF1- TF4 tablet formulations.

Fig. 10: % drug release of TF5- TF8 tablet formulations.

Analysis of Data

When the impact of these parameters on the percentage of drug release (Y1) was examined using a polynomial equation, it was discovered that Crospovidone, SSG, and Croscarmellose Sodium had a favorable effect on drug release. The impact of these superdisintegrants on Lasmiditan release was visualized using a three-dimensional response surface plot. When the concentrations of SSG, Croscarmellose Sodium, and Crospovidone were increased from 5 mg to 20 mg, the response curve for Y1 clearly indicated an increase in drug release, indicating that greater concentrations of these excipients enhance the drug's release rate.

Fig. 11: Contour plot of % drug release.

Fig. 12: 3D Response Surface Plot.

Using a polynomial equation to evaluate the effects of independent variables on friability (Y2), it was found that Crospovidone, SSG, and Croscarmellose Sodium had a negative effect on friability. A 3D response surface plot showed that friability clearly decreased when these excipient concentrations rose from 5 mg to 20 mg. With a high drug release rate of 94.19% and low friability of 0.36%, the eighth formulation run was found to be the most optimal by the statistical model, indicating better tablet strength and performance.

Fig. 13: Contour plot of friability.

Fig. 14: 3D Response Surface Plot.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The study successfully developed mucoadhesive buccal tablets of Lasmiditan using direct compression technique. FTIR and DSC studies confirmed that there was no interaction between the drug and excipients. All formulations showed good flow properties and acceptable tablet evaluation parameters. Drug content was found to be uniform in all batches. The concentration of superdisintegrants significantly affected the drug release pattern. Among all formulations, TF6 showed the highest drug release (94.19% in 30 minutes) with excellent mechanical strength and low friability. The optimized formulation demonstrated good stability, uniformity, and rapid drug release. Therefore, TF6 can be considered a promising mucoadhesive buccal tablet formulation for effective delivery of Lasmiditan.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In order to complete this experiment, the author would like to thank Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy, Manur (Kalwan) for supplying the necessary components and lab equipment.

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